

TITLE: Decline in Lead and the Rise of ASD: A Multiyear Natural Experiment at the US State Level

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Abstract

Background: The origins of the autism epidemic have thus far remained elusive. Paramount to protecting against future cases of this neurodevelopmental disorder is a better understanding of its etiology.

Methods: We conducted a natural experiment testing the hypothesis that lead (Pb) exposure inhibits future diagnosis of autism spectrum disorder (ASD). Annual percentage of children aged ≤ 6 years with elevated blood lead level (EBLL) of ≥ 10 ug/dl (EBLL-10) at the US state level from 1999-2005 was sourced from the Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Due to absence of data within these years, an approximated percentage of EBLL > 5 ug/dl was derived (EBLL-5D). These EBLL estimates (i.e., EBLL-10 and EBLL-5D), in combination with population density, were examined in time-series regression analyses against prevalence of ASD among students born from 1999-2005 and aged 6 years within corresponding years (i.e., 2005-2011).

Results: 37 states and the District of Columbia (DC), consisting of 236 observations over 7 years, met the conditions of the study. In regression analyses, population density (as quadratic variable) and EBLL-10 accounted for less than 20% of variance of the model (adj. $R^2 = 0.18$, $P < 0.0001$). However, in a model replacing EBLL-10 with EBLL-5D ($n = 229$), more than a third of variance was accounted for (adj. $R^2 = 0.34$, $P < 0.0001$), thus indicating high predictive value. In the latter model, EBLL was associated with decreased risk of ASD ($P < 0.0001$), even after controlling for year, while association with population was inversely U-shaped.

Conclusions: With considerable public health implications, perinatal lead exposure was demonstrated to be a potent inhibitor of ASD.

Background

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopment disorder with symptoms manifested in early childhood. It remains a matter of dispute as to whether the increasing prevalence of this disorder is genuine—that is, caused by an unknown mechanism—or is merely an artifact of changes in diagnostic definitions, earlier diagnosis, or increased popular awareness (1, 2). While some authors adhere to the latter argumentation, others consider these explanations to be insufficient and unable to account for most of the observed growth in ASD prevalence. Thus, some researchers have sought an additional explanation rooted in biologically plausible mechanisms, often based on environmental triggers (3).

Measured prevalence of autism was universally low in the early 1970s and steadily increased thereafter (4). In recent years, nations such as Japan, South Korea, Sweden, and USA have seen an ASD prevalence surpassing 2% and nearing or even exceeding 3% (5, 6, 7, 8, 9). Meanwhile other countries, such as China, Croatia, Ecuador, India, Oman, and Venezuela have observed dramatically lower rates (10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15). In fact, there is a difference of more than two orders of magnitude between the prevalence rates of Oman (1.4 per 10,000) and Goyang City, South Korea (264 per 10,000) within rather contemporaneous studies. Disparities within studies such as these have often been rationalized to result from cultural or socioeconomic differences (2, 16).

Though the etiology of ASD may be uncertain, we can surmise that a satisfactory explanation for the autism epidemic would: 1) resolve the temporal discrepancies in prevalence observed within each location where it has been periodically or regularly measured; 2) account for typically higher prevalence among younger cohorts within single epidemiological screenings; and 3)

explain observed geographical differences in prevalence which vary widely not just on the national level, but also on more regional scales (17).

Though some studies have identified environmental risk factors for ASD, none have satisfactorily met the above criteria to explain the onset and persistence of the epidemic. A wealth of literature can be found investigating the nature of exposure to toxic metals and their relationship to developmental delay; however, associations with ASD have been marked by inconsistency (18, 19, 20, 21). A recent study using tooth matrix biomarkers revealed that metal dysregulation arises early in the perinatal period among those with ASD, thus suggesting that an uncoupling may be occurring between external maternal metal exposure and subsequent metal levels observed within the developing child (22). This would suggest that studies examining metal levels directly in ASD children may be confounded, in part, from an altered uptake of metals rather than due to actual external differences in exposure.

Importantly, in a study by Schmidt and colleagues (2014), maternal perinatal iron (Fe) supplementation has been found to be associated with a significantly reduced risk of ASD in offspring (23). If one considers the larger context of an ever-increasing ASD prevalence and a decreasing prevalence of Fe deficiency in infants, women of child-bearing age, and pregnant women, it is unlikely that this finding by Schmidt can be explained simply from remedying Fe deficiency. Instead, Fe may have been acting as an effect modifier, feasibly decreasing exposure to a potentially toxic metal (24). This mechanism may be mediated via the divalent metal transporter-1 (DMT1). In fact, it has been found that low blood Fe levels lead to upregulation of intestinal DMT1 with increased subsequent absorption of other metals (25). Conversely, if levels of Fe are increased, downregulation of DMT1 places other metals at a disadvantage for passage through the transporter (26). The significance of DMT1 is further enhanced by its presence in the

placenta and mammary gland which may impact the developing fetus and infant, respectively (27).

The above hypothesis suggests that a complete picture of exposure to certain metals may be inadequate if measured without adjusting for the contextual relationship of other polluting metals (28). Indeed, this supposition would also presage the possibility that metals other than Fe may similarly downregulate DMT1 or other metal transporter and possess similar protective properties to that of Fe. Counterintuitively, a steep decline in exposure to lead (Pb) over the past few decades, due to concern over neurodevelopmental impairment, may have inadvertently led to the dramatic rise of ASD. Inoculation to ASD from maternal exposure to Pb may have prevented high exposure to the unidentified toxicant within the developing fetus and infant. The hypothesis suggests that countries that first eliminated leaded gasoline (the bulk source of Pb pollution in the modern era) would now see the highest levels of ASD. Accordingly, the disparate ASD prevalence rates specified above may be a consequence of duration of time from termination of leaded gasoline.

A satisfactory explanation for the ASD epidemic would resolve the temporal and geographic discrepancies in ASD prevalence. This could be manifested not just at the national level, but also within geographic borders where generally homogenous methods for diagnosing ASD exist. With this understanding, the following natural experiment attempts to explain the variation in ASD prevalence among US states and across time by considering differences in Pb exposures.

1 Methods

We conducted a time-series natural experiment (ecological study) at the US state level to investigate the ability of blood lead level (BLL) and population density to explain annual variation in ASD prevalence.

1.1 EBLL-10 threshold.

The annual ASD count of students aged six years for the years 2005-2011 were sourced from part B of the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act (IDEA) which contains information on all students with disabilities identified with autism within each state. It was necessary to limit the study to these years as only in these years were single year counts available. To derive annual prevalence, ASD counts were divided by total first grade student enrollment for respective states and years and which were sourced from the National Center for Education Statistics (29, 30).

As a child's BLL correlates well to that of their mother and due to the high number of children tested annually within each state, elevated BLL ≥ 10 $\mu\text{g/dL}$ (EBLL-10) among children aged <72 months served as a surrogate of perinatal BLL (31, 32). These data were available annually by state for years 1999-2005 (i.e., corresponding to the birth years of students aged 6 years) from a 1997-2015 dataset sourced from the Center for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) (33, 34). While children's BLL is typically lower than adult BLL, it was necessary to determine only the relative BLL among states.

Since it was essential to understand the putative inhibitory effects of BLL within the context of exposure to ASD-causing toxicants, and with vehicle emissions potentially being the main source of this pollutant, we used population density as a proxy indicator (35). Pollutants from

vehicle emissions may include not just tailpipe emissions, but also non-exhaust emissions from tires, brakes, and road surface (36). As the latter emissions are more concentrated in metals, it is these that we are more interested in investigating (37). Mean ZIP-code tabulation area (ZCTA)-level population density (persons per square mile [PPSM]) was weighted by population. These data were derived for each state from US census year 2010, which was extracted from the Missouri Census Data Center (38).

To understand the strength of association between EBLL-10 and population density, Pearson correlation coefficient was assessed. Least squares linear regression models were fitted with the square root of ASD prevalence serving as the dependent variable and EBLL-10 and population density as independent variables. Analysis was limited to those years in which at least 2% of the states' children's population were tested for BLL. Distribution of population density prompted the application of a quadratic term in the model. As the District of Columbia (DC) and New York were outliers in population density, a second model was developed without these locations.

1.2 EBLL-5D threshold.

As the rate of EBLL-5 for years 1999-2005 was not available, and as EBLL-10 was deemed to too high a threshold to accurately assess perinatal Pb, we derived an approximation for EBLL-5 for these years (EBLL-5D). This was accomplished by first obtaining a mean ratio of EBLL-5 to EBLL-10 (5:10 ratio) for the years 2010-2015. EBLL data for the years 2012-2015 was supplemented from an additional 2012-2018 CDC dataset (39). If the 2012-2018 dataset contained higher representation of children for the years 2012-2015, then these data were applied. In addition, only estimates in which $\geq 3\%$ of the total children aged <72 months were

tested were applied towards the 5:10 ratio. This 5:10 ratio was multiplied by EBLL-10 from 1999-2005 for each observation and then normalized, in accordance with the following equation:

$$Y = 1 - (e^{-(a*b)}) \quad (1)$$

where, $Y = \text{EBLL-5D}$; $a = 5:10$ ratio; and $b = \text{annual EBLL-10 from 1999-2005}$. The theory behind transforming the data using the 5:10 ratio above is that BLL in each state follows a different distribution curve. Specifically, exposure to Pb creates relatively stable distribution patterns which are maintained over time and depend on a community's proximity to sources of ambient Pb emissions or exposure to Pb-based plumbing and paint. Only states in which $\geq 2\%$ of the children's population had BLL measurements were applied, however scenario analyses incorporating all available observations were conducted.

As a proof-of-concept, the 5:10 ratio was derived for all states with two or more EBLL-10 and EBLL-5 observations from 2013-2015. With the above equation (1), EBLL-5D estimates were then derived for years 2010-2012 only using states in which $\geq 2\%$ of the children's population had BLL measurements. A Pearson correlation analysis was performed which indicated high correlation ($n=79$, 0.8501 , $P < 0.0001$). Least squares regression analysis found a significant association, though actual EBLL-5 observations were higher than derived estimates (regression coefficient: 1.1009 , $P < 0.0001$).

To understand the relationship between EBLL-5D and population density, Pearson correlation of EBLL-5D and population density was assessed. Geospatial analysis was conducted in ArcGIS Pro using the global Moran's I statistic (contiguity edges corners method) for both EBLL-5D and ASD within two time periods. As there were fewer than 30 observations during the first year, we used the first instance of EBLL-5D from 1999-2005 (hereafter, 1999 estimates) or first instance

of ASD estimates from 2005-2011 (hereafter, 2005 estimates). Final year estimates were only from 2005 and 2011 for EBLL-5D and ASD, respectively. Anselin Moran cluster analyses were conducted to determine high-high, low-low, high-low, and low-high region of spatial autocorrelation.

Next, least squares linear regression models were developed with the square root of ASD prevalence serving as the dependent variable and EBLL-5D and population density as independent variables. Distribution of population density prompted the application of a quadratic term in the model. Several scenario models incorporating EBLL-5D were developed including removing outlier states with high population density (i.e., DC and New York) as well as models with cut-offs of EBLL-5D of $\geq 20\%$, $\geq 30\%$, and $\geq 40\%$. Additional models were fitted with population density thresholds (< 500 , < 1000 , < 2000 PPSM). All models were controlled for schoolyear.

1.3 Statistical Analysis.

Adjusted coefficient of determination (R^2) was used to provide a measure of the explanatory power of the models. All regressions analyses were ordinary least squares and were performed with SAS University Edition. To evaluate the existence of geographical patterns in Pb exposure and prevalence of ASD, annual choropleths were developed. No imputation was carried out for missing data on covariates. Computer code is available from the corresponding author by request.

2 Results

2.1 EBLL-10 threshold.

With a total of 50 US states and the District of Columbia (DC), there were 357 possible observations for analysis over the seven-year study period. Student counts of ASD were obtained from nearly all potential observations (98.6%, $n = 352$). Of these, 67.0% ($n = 236$) had corresponding rates of EBLL-10 (37 states and DC, Table 1). Within these 236 observations from 2005-2011, over 19,802,839 students aged six were represented, with 144,390 (0.73%) of these students diagnosed with ASD. Mean ASD prevalence increased from 0.49% (SD: 0.23%) in 2005 to 0.81% (SD: 0.33%) in 2011. Mean EBLL-10 fell from 4.52% (SD: 2.98%) in 1999 to 1.48% (SD: 1.10%) in 2005. No correlation was found between EBLL-10 and population density ($r = 0.0117$, $P = 0.8583$). Figures 1, 2, and 3, provide choropleths of ASD prevalence, EBLL-10, and population density, respectively, over the study period.

Upon univariate analysis, no association between EBLL-10 and ASD prevalence was found. However, after applying population density to the model (using quadratic term), population density was associated with ASD in an inverse U-shape ($P < 0.0001$) while EBLL-10 trended towards a negative association ($P = 0.2171$, Table 2). After removing DC and New York observations from the model as population density outliers, EBLL-10 was found to be significantly inversely associated with ASD ($P = 0.0077$), though this relationship failed to hold after controlling for year. Both population density and EBLL-10 accounted for less than 20% of variance of the model (adj. $R^2 = 0.1838$, $P < 0.0001$).

2.2 EBL-5D threshold.

From the EBL-10 estimates included in the above analysis, a total of 229 observations (36 states and DC) of EBL-5D were derived. Figure 4 depicts the change in EBL-5D estimates over the study period. Overall mean EBL-5D fell from 35.3% (SD: 21.7%) in 1999 to 13.7% (SD: 11.4%) in 2005. Mississippi had the highest observed level of EBL-5, estimated at over 90% in 1999. This corresponded to an ASD prevalence of 0.12% in 2005. In contrast, Delaware saw the lowest derived estimate of EBL-5 at 3.1% in 2005; this corresponded to 0.86% with ASD in 2011. The highest ASD prevalence was found in Minnesota at 1.45% in 2009 with a corresponding EBL-5 of 12.3% in 2003. In contrast, the lowest ASD prevalence was observed in Oklahoma at 0.07% in 2005 with a corresponding EBL-5D of 12.5% in 1999.

In Figures 5A and 5B, ASD prevalence is plotted by EBL-5D and population density, respectively. A negative correlation was found between EBL-5D and population density ($r = -0.1671$, $P = 0.0113$). Global Moran's I found 2005 (Moran's index: 0.2894, $P = 0.0042$) and 2011 (Moran's index: 0.2835, $P = 0.0076$) ASD estimates to be spatially correlated. Both 1999 EBL-5D (Moran's index: 0.2122, $P = 0.0275$) and 2005 EBL-5D estimates were also spatially correlated (Moran's index: 0.1523, $P = 0.0409$). Anselin Moran cluster analysis (Figure 6) conducted with ASD estimates found low-low clusters in the Southeast as well as centered around Nebraska and Colorado in 2005. High-high clusters were found in the Northeast in 2011. A low-low cluster of EBL-5D was located in the Southwest in 1999 and the Midwest in 2005.

Several least squares models were fitted with differing criteria (Table 3). On univariate regression, EBL-5D alone explained 12% of the variance of the model (adj. $R^2 = 0.1222$, $P < 0.0001$) which increased to 34% (adj. $R^2 = 0.3423$, $P < 0.0001$) after controlling for population

density (with quadratic term). After removing DC and New York as outliers in population density, the fitted model explained over half of the variance of ASD prevalence ($n = 216$, $\text{adj. } R^2 = 0.5240$, $P < 0.0001$). Moreover, EBLL-5D remained significantly protective of ASD ($P < 0.0001$ in each model) after controlling for year. When limiting the univariate models to those observations with EBLL-5D $\geq 20\%$ ($n = 97$), $\geq 30\%$ ($n = 51$) and $\geq 40\%$ ($n = 24$), adjusted R^2 increased to 0.5794, 0.7211, and 0.7727, respectively ($P < 0.0001$, for each). Upon limiting population density to < 500 PPSM ($n = 25$), < 1000 PPSM ($n = 67$), and < 2000 PPSM ($n = 151$), adjusted R^2 was 0.6631, 0.4732, and 0.4862, respectively ($P < 0.0001$, for each). EBLL-5D remained associated with decreased ASD prevalence after controlling for year in each model.

3 Discussion

This is the first population-level study investigating the effect of perinatal exposure to Pb on subsequent risk of ASD. The relationship of ASD prevalence to EBLL was investigated at the US state level in a time-series analysis over seven years. In this natural experiment, the inverse association observed between Pb and ASD is highly suggestive that Pb is a potent inhibitor of ASD. Although EBLL-10 was generally declining with each consecutive year, multicollinearity of these two covariates undercut potential association of EBLL-10 with ASD. However, within the EBLL-5D model, controlling for year did not dissolve its association with ASD, thus demonstrating that the observed relationship was temporally robust and geographically robust. Overall, it indicates that the deliberate pursuit in the decline of Pb in the built environment over recent decades due to concerns of childhood toxicity, may have paradoxically, and tragically, generated the current autism epidemic.

These findings provide for considerable understanding of the current autism epidemic. As levels of Pb exposure declined with the phase-out of leaded gasoline, ASD began to rise from a prevalence more than two orders of magnitude lower than current rates (40). The phase-out of leaded gasoline occurred in accordance with country-specific regulations, with early adopters employing completely lead-free gasoline before the turn of the millennium but with other nations lagging until more recently (41). Divergence in use of unleaded gasoline, paint, and plumbing yielded global differences in BLL and gave rise to much of the disparity in ASD prevalence seen in contemporaneously conducted studies (42). Nations with a high prevalence of ASD, such as Japan, Korea, Sweden, and the US, banned or completely phased-out leaded gasoline from the market within the 1980's to early 1990's. This had profound impact on BLL, which in 1976 was above 15 µg/dl in the US, but by 1980 had already dropped to below 10 µg/dl (43). However, in Croatia, Ecuador, Oman, and Venezuela—nations with rather low estimates of ASD prevalence, as described earlier—the maximum content of lead in gasoline in 1996 was 0.60, 0.50, 0.62, and 0.85 g/l, respectively, with presumably higher BLL (43).

Few studies measuring maternal Pb levels and subsequent risk of ASD have been conducted. As Pb is thought to lead to neurological deficits, it has often been assumed that any association of this toxic metal towards risk of ASD would be necessarily contributory rather than inhibitory (44). Notably, results from the current study align with one recent Norwegian perinatal study which found mean BLL lower in ASD cases than controls (8.35 µg/L [7.97, 8.75] vs. 8.82 µg/L [8.60, 9.05], respectively), though 95% intervals are overlapping (45). Postnatal studies of Pb are more common and results are often mixed, with some findings being in contrast to the present study (46, 47, 48), while others are more aligned (49, 50). In a perinatal study of dental metal levels, Arora et al. found increased Pb among ASD twins compared to non-ASD siblings (22).

However, altered dental enamel—marked by the presence of accentuated lines caused by physiological stress or undernourishment—has been found in children with autism (51). Such early dysregulation continuing through childhood may confound dental analyses. Metal studies using other matrices may be confounded by altered bone development—a critical depository of Pb and other metals—in children with ASD (52).

The current study also found a positive association between population density and ASD at lower densities and peaking at around 2000 PPSM; thereafter, ASD declined with increasing density. This partially aligns with literature. For instance, in Denmark, Lauritsen et al. found a progressively increased risk of ASD in accordance with urbanicity, with higher degree of urbanization of both residence at birth and childhood equating to higher risk of ASD (53). A recent study from Egypt found urban residence was more associated with ASD than rural residence (54). Similarly, a study from Taiwan found greater incidence of ASD among children in satellite and urban communities than rural areas(55). While many aspects of urbanicity could potentially be associated with ASD, air pollution has been well-studied as a contributing factor. Investigators have previously observed a link between traffic-related air pollution and autism(56, 57). A meta-analysis by Dutheil et al. found maternal exposure to particulate matter <math><2.5\mu\text{m}</math> (PM2.5) of greatest risk (58). Third trimester exposure of PM2.5 has also been associated with the greatest risk (59). Nitric oxide (NO), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), and carbon monoxide (CO), each associated with traffic, have also been implicated as risk factors (56, 60, 61).

The decreasing prevalence of ASD seen with larger population densities may be due to several causes. First, there are numerous other pollutants the developing child may be exposed to from point sources that are commonly produced from industry in highly urbanized areas. The totality of these pollutants may have an overall mitigating effect on risk of ASD. Second, individuals

living in urban environments may be exposed to fewer drinking water pollutants due to more aggressively treated water. Third, underdiagnosis of ASD may occur within districts of particularly high levels of the unknown toxicant if it leads to multiple neurodevelopmental disorders (e.g., attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder [ADHD]) with the potential to obscure a diagnosis of ASD, at least at an early age (62). A final interpretation for the downwardly sloping curve is a consequence of higher efficiencies in transportation with increasing population density. Interestingly, in a study from Japan by Matsuhashi et al., the authors found that CO₂ emissions (as measured by mileage per vehicle) were also inversely U-shaped—peaking at a population density of 100-1000 persons/km² and thereafter declining (35). Thus, fuel exhaust and non-exhaust vehicle emissions, including tire, brake wear, and road surface wear may play a role in contributing towards ASD risk (36). However, it is unlikely that ground exposure to vehicles emissions within highly urbanized areas are lower than that of less urbanized regions. Therefore, we can surmise that perinatal exposure may arise from increased vehicle emissions within the vehicle cabin, or, alternatively, the vertical structure of highly urbanized areas may decrease overall exposure to emissions.

Higher explanatory value, as determined by adjusted R², was observed in those models limited to states having higher EBLL as well as lower population densities. At lower perinatal BLL exposure, infants may effectively be exposed to an increasing number and higher dosage of other metals via gut metal transporters. They may also potentially be subject to increased fluctuations to in-utero Pb. At higher population densities, as previously mentioned, there may be an increased number of sources of pollution which may ultimately lead to extremes in direct exposure to the unknown metal toxicant or modifications of exposure via other metals. Thus, low EBLL and high population density may ultimately reduce any potential association with ASD.

The latest Autism and Developmental Disabilities Monitoring Network (ADDM) estimate for ASD prevalence based on children aged 8 years in 2020 was 2.8%, ranging from 2.3% in Maryland to 4.5% in California (63). Whereas the lowest EBL-5D estimate in the current study was from Delaware at 3.1% and corresponded to an ASD prevalence of 0.86%, when children in the ADDM study were born (i.e., 2012), the overall US EBL-5 was somewhat higher at 5.2% (39). While this may suggest that levels of ASD are swelling beyond that which would be expected based on the drop in BLL alone, it should be noted that EBL-5 in the present study was derived and are expected to be somewhat lower than actual EBL-5 data, in accordance with the proof-of-concept study. It is also conceivable that maternal perinatal BLL has recently declined faster than children's BLL. However, the current study saw all but four observations of EBL-5D above 5%, and most well above this mark. Thus, much of the surge in prevalence may be due to an exponential rise in ASD as perinatal BLL falls to zero.

Due to the ecological nature of the study, it is important to address factors that may confound the results. Each time-series analysis was controlled for year to ensure that changes in Pb were not coincidentally aligned with other increasing or decreasing pollutants as well as to control for changes in diagnostic criteria or diagnostic fashion. Thus, any confounding environmental factors must confront the diminished likelihood of being exquisitely correlated to Pb in geography and time. Still, confounders may persist with the use of population density as a metric for estimating vehicle pollution exposure.

There are several limitations to this study. Within each state, the number of persons with measured BLL as a percentage of the population differed. Locations with higher populations are also likely to have more accurate BLL or ASD prevalence rates (i.e., narrower 95% confident intervals). However, regions in these investigations are weighted similarly, independent of

population. In addition, as proxy perinatal blood levels are at the population level, children who either moved away from or into any of the regions of interest could lead to a discrepancy between ASD prevalence rate and putative Pb exposure. Only those children who were enrolled in schools were counted towards ASD prevalence rates. The changing fashion in diagnosing ASD over the study time period and heterogeneity in applying the definitions of ASD in disparate locations are other known factors which can lead to varying levels of ASD (64, 65).

Public health implications resulting from this research are vast. Much has been gained by the removal of this toxicant over the decades, particularly in reducing acute Pb poisoning.

Considerable research has been conducted which has generally suggested lower Pb enables improved child cognitive development (66). Together, these reasons are the impetus for the ongoing deliberate removal of Pb from the built environment. However, we must consider the fate of children in the coming years and decades who will be born into a low Pb environment with the foreknowledge that this may place the child at greater risk of ASD. This should be weighed against the risks of being exposed to excessive Pb. In particular, the socioeconomic burden of increasing ASD prevalence may be greater than perceived benefits of lower Pb exposure. Of course, we may not face such a stark choice between decreasing the risk of ASD or increasing an infant's mental development. Further research may reveal other, potentially safer, metal inhibitors of ASD. For instance, as had been previously argued, maternal Fe supplementation may reduce risk of ASD even in mothers without Fe deficiency (23, 24). In addition to employing inhibitors of ASD, we can reduce exposures to vehicle emissions. Metal emissions from tires, breaks, and road surfaces may be the largest source of ASD-causing toxicants (36).

We must also reassess prior studies which have investigated the impact of BLL on childhood performance (66). As ASD is often associated with lower IQ, these studies may in part be influenced by the increased number of children with ASD at the lowest perinatal BLLs (67). It should be noted that the influence of BLL on IQ has mostly been observed in postnatal rather than perinatal measurements of BLL (68). Even without any direct influence from children with ASD, these investigations may not fully assess the countervailing effect of lower BLL on exposure to other pollutants—namely, increased metal exposure, such as manganese, which in excess may affect neurodevelopment (69). Perhaps part of the reason why most of the decline in IQ scores occurs at the lowest levels of blood Pb is due to such influence from other metals (66, 70, 71).

In summary, though it has been generally acknowledged that genetic and environmental interactions are causal of ASD, knowledge of which environmental factors contributed to the condition has eluded researchers. Though these results contrast with how Pb is typically perceived, namely, as detrimental to normal neurodevelopment, we can now advance the notion that Pb may be protective of ASD and the long-term and ongoing reduction in Pb exposure has likely been the primary cause of the epidemic, though not the ultimate cause of ASD. We must face the prospect that continuation of the policy of removing Pb from the built environment will lead to increased cases of ASD.

Conflict of Interest.

None declared.

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Data Availability.

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Tables

Table 1. State- and year-level summary of included observations over 7-year study period

	Observations* (n)	Range (%), ASD prevalence (2005-2011)	Range (%), children <6 yrs. tested	Range (%), EBLL-10 (1999-2005)	Ratio, 5:10 EBLL	Range (%), EBLL-5D (1999-2005)	Population Density
State-level summary							
Alabama	7	0.22-0.50	3.59-6.30	1.37-5.30	7.5	9.8-32.9	619.7
Arizona	2	0.65-0.74	2.59-6.26	0.61-1.89	7.1	4.2-12.5	2690.0
California	3	1.11-1.14	7.70-16.43	0.74-1.10	15.6	10.9-15.8	5687.5
Colorado	1	0.32	2.42	1.26	12.8	14.9	2485.3
Connecticut	7	0.73-1.26	23.94-26.87	1.89-3.67	7.5	13.1-23.9	2579.6
District of Columbia	6	0.32-.078	23.5-46.1	0.77-2.09	6.0	4.5-11.8	13,856.3
Delaware	7	0.49-0.86	11.29-23.33	0.46-2.72	6.8	3.1-16.9	1851.4
Florida	7	0.44-0.95	2.99-9.68	0.28-4.39	18.2	5.0-55.0	2897.9
Georgia	7	0.39-0.49	2.97-8.90	0.33-2.49	18.6	5.9-37.0	1255.0
Illinois	7	0.52-0.68	10.96-20.12	4.98-11.33	6.2	26.7-50.7	5146.0
Indiana	7	0.64-0.92	4.97-8.53	1.28-2.90	8.5	10.3-21.9	1093.3
Iowa	7	0.10-0.19	12.63-21.97	2.00-3.81	57.2	68.2-88.7	708.2
Kansas	6	0.35-0.53	3.19-12.31	1.10-3.06	8.6	9.1-23.2	175.8
Kentucky	5	0.36-0.52	5.10-8.70	0.67-1.30	8.7	5.7-10.7	438.0
Louisiana	7	0.30-0.43	5.71-18.05	1.01-3.32	11.6	11.0-31.9	1361.2
Maine	7	0.91-1.65	11.76-17.16	1.74-3.50	-	-	507.3
Maryland	6	0.69-0.91	15.54-23.84	1.21-5.38	7.8	9.1-34.4	3133.4
Massachusetts	7	0.69-1.31	49.90-55.04	0.92-2.03	11.3	9.9-20.5	4914.7
Michigan	7	0.53-0.77	8.61-16.87	2.63-7.97	7.9	18.8-46.7	1862.0
Minnesota	7	0.95-1.45	9.47-19.28	0.85-3.31	10.1	8.2-28.3	1823.5
Mississippi	7	0.12-0.35	3.26-16.97	0.94-9.65	24.1	20.3-90.3	375.3
Missouri	7	0.53-0.81	11.21-17.80	2.29-9.77	9.2	19.0-59.3	1400.0
New Hampshire	7	0.37-0.77	14.55-16.29	2.25-3.87	12.1	23.8-37.3	871.3
New Jersey	6	1.00-1.32	19.85-25.50	1.26-2.83	6.9	8.3-17.8	6010.3
New Mexico	2	0.17-0.24	2.07-2.84	0.62-0.71	11.0	6.6-7.5	971.7
New York	7	0.59-1.02	22.26-24.58	1.31-3.41	6.9	8.6-21.0	21,634.9
North Carolina	7	0.36-0.65	3.40-18.82	0.37-1.08	20.8	7.4-20.1	811.8
Ohio	7	0.47-0.84	12.73-17.28	2.55-8.23	7.1	16.5-44.0	1711.5
Oklahoma	7	0.07-0.28	3.10-7.55	0.99-1.62	9.1	8.6-13.7	1002.2
Oregon	7	0.85-1.30	2.34-4.85	0.53-1.82	13.9	7.1-22.4	1910.5
Pennsylvania	7	0.71-1.39	5.33-16.64	4.67-9.84	6.5	26.3-47.4	3342.4
Rhode Island	7	0.64-1.08	40.86-46.40	2.92-6.85	6.7	17.9-36.9	4229.3
Tennessee	7	0.27-0.53	2.17-12.47	0.45-6.75	17.9	7.7-70.1	892.7
Texas	5	0.52-0.69	8.79-13.70	0.51-1.05	10.9	5.4-10.8	2236.1
Vermont	5	0.34-0.66	15.44-22.59	1.34-2.75	14.5	17.7-32.9	623.2

Virginia	7	0.46-0.90	4.49-11.49	0.76-2.39	12.2	8.8-25.3	1888.8
West Virginia	7	0.36-0.64	7.83-11.99	0.83-1.74	9.5	7.6-15.2	400.4
Wisconsin	7	0.70-1.00	16.99-19.94	2.70-6.46	8.1	19.7-40.8	1703.5
Year-level summary							
2005	30	0.07-0.95	2.17-55.04	0.62-11.33	-	6.6-90.3	175.8-21,634.9
2006	33	0.08-1.15	2.07-53.13	0.71-9.41	-	7.2-86.6	175.8-21,634.9
2007	34	0.13-1.28	2.42-51.18	0.82-9.41	-	5.6-80.9	175.8-21,634.9
2008	33	0.10-1.40	2.59-50.46	0.75-9.84	-	4.5-78.3	175.8-21,634.9
2009	35	0.10-1.52	4.21-49.90	0.61-8.14	-	5.7-74.8	175.8-21,634.9
2010	35	0.11-1.65	3.40-50.30	0.47-6.33	-	5.91-71.6	175.8-21,634.9
2011	36	0.11-1.39	4.42-50.10	0.28-4.98	-	3.1-68.2	175.8-21,634.9

*EBLL-5 analyses excluded in Maine due to lack of EBLL-5 estimates.

EBLL-10: Elevated blood lead level ≥ 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$; EBLL-5D: Derived prevalence of elevated blood lead level ≥ 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$; Population density; weighted average of persons per square mile.

Table 2. Linear regression models of sqrt (ASD) with EBLL-10.

Model Criteria	Variable	Model: EBLL-10 only				Model: EBLL-10, adjusted for Population Density				Model: EBLL-10, adjusted for Population density and Year			
		Coefficient	SE	T-Value	P-Value	Coefficient	SE	T-Value	P-Value	Coefficient	SE	T-Value	P-Value
All Observations (n=236)	Intercept	0.08002	0.00214	37.35	<0.0001	0.06909	0.00242	28.51	<0.0001	-7.12167	1.29864	-5.48	<0.0001
	EBLL-10	0.00762	0.06269	0.12	0.9033	-0.07164	0.05788	-1.24	0.2171	0.07214	0.06037	1.19	0.2333
	Density	-	-	-	-	7.27E-06	1.02E-06	7.12E+00	<0.0001	6.44E-06	9.73E-07	6.62E+00	<0.0001
	Density * Density	-	-	-	-	-3.05E-10	4.98E-11	-6.13E+00	<0.0001	-2.65E-10	4.74E-11	-5.58E+00	<0.0001
	Year	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.00359	6.48E-04	5.54	<0.0001
	Adjusted R-Square (P-value)	-0.0042 (P = 0.9033)				0.1838 (P < 0.0001)				0.2763 (P < 0.0001)			
Excluding District of Columbia and New York (n=223)	Intercept	0.07956	0.00223	35.6	<0.0001	0.05945	0.00319	18.66	<0.0001	-6.21242	1.26725	-4.9	<0.0001
	EBLL-10	0.01412	0.0641	0.22	0.8259	-0.1495	0.05554	-2.69	0.0077	-0.02081	0.05884	-0.35	0.7239
	Density	-	-	-	-	1.86E-05	2.95E-06	6.32E+00	<0.0001	1.76E-05	2.81E-06	6.25E+00	<0.0001
	Density * Density	-	-	-	-	-1.91E-09	4.94E-10	-3.87E+00	0.0001	-1.85E-09	4.70E-10	-3.94E+00	0.0001
	Year	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.00313	6.33E-04	4.95	<0.0001
	Adjusted R-Square (P-value)	-0.0043 (P = 0.9816)				0.3104 (P < 0.0001)				0.3772 (P < 0.0001)			

EBLL-10: Elevated blood lead level ≥ 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$; sqrt: square root; Year: Year of derived ASD prevalence.

Table 3. Linear regression models of sqrt (ASD) with EBLL-5D.

Model Criteria*	Variable	Model: EBLL-5D only				Model: + adjusted for Population Density				Model: + adjusted for Population density and Year			
		Coefficient	SE	T-Value	P-Value	Coefficient	SE	T-Value	P-Value	Coefficient	SE	T-Value	P-Value
Model #1 (n=229)	Intercept	0.08914	0.00215	41.54	<0.0001	0.07382	0.00255	28.97	<0.0001	-4.67711	1.17005	-4	<0.0001
	EBLL-5D	-0.04471	0.00781	-5.72	<0.0001	-0.03793	0.00686	-5.53	<0.0001	-0.02578	0.00728	-3.54	0.0005
	Density	-	-	-	-	0.00000764	8.86E-07	8.63	<0.0001	7.57E-06	8.57E-07	8.83	<0.0001
	Density * Density	-	-	-	-	-3.27E-10	4.29E-11	-7.64	<0.0001	-3.21E-10	4.15E-11	-7.73	<0.0001
	Year	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.00237	0.00058408	4.06	<0.0001
	Adjusted R-Square (P-value)	0.1222 (P < 0.0001)				0.3423 (P < 0.0001)				0.3847 (P < 0.0001)			
Model #2 (n=216)	Intercept	0.08908	0.00227	39.27	<0.0001	0.0605	0.00299	20.23	<0.0001	-4.38537	1.03828	-4.22	<0.0001
	EBLL-5D	-0.04466	0.00806	-5.54	<0.0001	-0.04041	0.00594	-6.8	<0.0001	-0.02912	0.00629	-4.63	<0.0001
	Density	-	-	-	-	2.13E-05	2.38E-06	8.93	<0.0001	2.17E-05	2.29E-06	9.45	<0.0001
	Density * Density	-	-	-	-	-2.33E-09	4.00E-10	-5.83	<0.0001	-2.42E-09	3.86E-10	-6.28	<0.0001
	Year	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.00222	0.00051826	4.28	<0.0001
	Adjusted R-Square (P-value)	0.1213 (P < 0.0001)				0.5240 (P < 0.0001)				0.5599 (P < 0.0001)			
Model #3 (n=97)	Intercept	0.09833	0.00403	24.41	<0.0001	0.00072	0.01245	0.06	0.954	-3.1256	1.40121	-2.23	0.0281
	EBLL-5D	-0.06532	0.01021	-6.4	<0.0001	-0.05357	0.00801	-6.69	<0.0001	-0.05006	0.008	-6.25	<0.0001
	ln (Density)	-	-	-	-	0.01275	0.00158	8.09	<0.0001	0.01308	0.00155	8.44	<0.0001
	Year	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.00156	0.000699	2.23	0.0281
		Adjusted R-Square (P-value)	0.2938 (P < 0.0001)				0.5794 (P < 0.0001)				0.5965 (P < 0.0001)		
Model #4 (n=51)	Intercept	0.10493	0.00682	15.38	<0.0001	-0.03636	0.01819	-2	0.0511	-0.06604	2.00498	-0.03	0.9739
	EBLL-5D	-0.07733	0.01397	-5.54	<0.0001	-0.04486	0.01012	-4.43	<0.0001	-0.04487	0.01023	-4.39	<0.0001
	ln (Density)	-	-	-	-	0.01719	0.00214	8.02	<0.0001	0.01718	0.00217	7.91	<0.0001
	Year	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1.48E-05	0.001	0.01	0.9883
		Adjusted R-Square (P-value)	0.3677 (P < 0.0001)				0.7211 (P < 0.0001)				0.7152 (P < 0.0001)		
Model #5 (n=24)	Intercept	0.13246	0.01185	11.18	<0.0001	-0.02886	0.04018	-0.72	0.4806	0.94649	2.9064	0.33	0.7481
	EBLL-5D	-0.11684	0.0193	-6.05	<0.0001	-0.05883	0.02035	-2.89	0.0087	-0.05898	0.0208	-2.84	0.0102

	In (Density)	-	-	-	-	0.01753	0.00425	4.12	0.0005	0.01726	0.00442	3.91	0.0009
	Year	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-0.00049	0.00145	-0.34	0.7407
Adjusted R-Square (P-value)		0.6077 (P < 0.0001)				0.7727 (P < 0.0001)				0.7627 (P < 0.0001)			
Model #6 (n=25)	Intercept	0.07228	0.00189	38.18	<0.0001	0.07254	0.00503	14.41	<0.0001	-1.82122	1.51065	-1.21	0.2414
	EBLL-5D	-0.05165	0.0072	-7.17	<0.0001	-0.05166	0.00736	-7.01	<0.0001	-0.04703	0.00816	-5.76	<0.0001
	Density	-	-	-	-	-7.36E-07	1.33E-05	-0.06	0.9563	4.37E-07	1.31E-05	0.03	0.9738
	Year	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.000945	0.000754	1.25	0.2238
	Adjusted R-Square (P-value)	0.6777 (P < 0.0001)				0.6631 (P < 0.0001)				0.6716 (P < 0.0001)			
Model #7 (n=67)	Intercept	0.07341	0.00202	36.28	<0.0001	0.06726	0.00375	17.95	<0.0001	-3.90478	1.24215	-3.14	0.0025
	EBLL-5D	-0.0428	0.00576	-7.43	<0.0001	-0.04446	0.00571	-7.79	<0.0001	-0.03954	0.00555	-7.12	<0.0001
	Density	-	-	-	-	1.08E-05	5.57E-06	1.93	0.0577	1.20E-05	5.22E-06	2.3	0.0246
	Year	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.00198	0.00062012	3.2	0.0022
	Adjusted R-Square (P-value)	0.4511 (P < 0.0001)				0.4732 (P < 0.0001)				0.5369 (P < 0.0001)			
Model #8 (n=151)	Intercept	0.08322	0.00251	33.12	<0.0001	0.05742	0.00324	17.7	<0.0001	-4.25457	1.22243	-3.48	0.0007
	EBLL-5D	-0.04479	0.00858	-5.22	<0.0001	-0.03838	0.0067	-5.73	<0.0001	-0.02889	0.00699	-4.13	<0.0001
	Density	-	-	-	-	2.12E-05	2.13E-06	9.95	<0.0001	2.17E-05	2.06E-06	10.55	<0.0001
	Year	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.00215	0.0006102	3.53	0.0006
	Adjusted R-Square (P-value)	0.1489 (P < 0.0001)				0.4862 (P < 0.0001)				0.5236 (P < 0.0001)			
Model #9 (n=239)	Intercept	0.08839	0.00211	41.89	<0.0001	0.07302	0.00252	28.94	<0.0001	-5.18547	1.14026	-4.55	<0.0001
	EBLL-5D	-0.04415	0.00776	-5.69	<0.0001	-0.03711	0.00684	-5.43	<0.0001	-0.02372	0.00717	-3.31	0.0011
	Density	-	-	-	-	7.62E-06	8.81E-07	8.65	<0.0001	7.53E-06	8.45E-07	8.91	<0.0001
	Density * Density	-	-	-	-	-3.25E-10	4.27E-11	-7.61	<0.0001	-3.17E-10	4.10E-11	-7.74	<0.0001
	Year	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.00263	0.00056923	4.61	<0.0001
Adjusted R-Square (P-value)	0.1166 (P < 0.0001)				0.3333 (P < 0.0001)				0.3862 (P < 0.0001)				
Model #10 (n=253)	Intercept	0.08522	0.00197	43.26	<0.0001	0.07063	0.00227	31.18	<0.0001	-5.64966	1.08122	-5.23	<0.0001
	EBLL-5D	-0.02821	0.00658	-4.29	<0.0001	-0.02906	0.00568	-5.11	<0.0001	-0.01631	0.00591	-2.76	0.0062
	Density	-	-	-	-	7.88E-06	8.43E-07	9.35	<0.0001	7.71E-06	8.02E-07	9.61	<0.0001
	Density * Density	-	-	-	-	-3.34E-10	4.12E-11	-8.1	<0.0001	-3.23E-10	3.92E-11	-8.23	<0.0001
	Year	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.00286	0.00053981	5.29	<0.0001

Adjusted *R*-Square
(*P*-value)

0.0645 (*P* < 0.0001)

0.3143 (*P* < 0.0001)

0.3814 (*P* < 0.0001)

*Model Criteria:

#1: All observations (Percentage of children BLL tested: $\geq 2.0\%$)

#2: Excluding District of Columbia (DC) and New York

#3: EBL-5D: $\geq 20\%$

#4: EBL-5D: $\geq 30\%$

#5: EBL-5D: $\geq 40\%$

#6: Population density: <500 PPSM

#7: Population density: <1000 PPSM

#8: Population density: <2000 PPSM

#9: Percentage of children BLL tested: $\geq 1.0\%$

#10: Percentage of children BLL tested: All ($> 0.0\%$)

Model #6 dependent variable was fitted with ASD prevalence. All other models were fitted with square root transformed ASD prevalence. EBL-5D: Derived prevalence of elevated blood lead level $\geq 5 \mu\text{g/dl}$; sqrt: square root; ln: natural log; Density: Population density; PPSM: persons per square mile; Year: Year of derived ASD prevalence.

Figures

Figure 1. Choropleth of mean state ASD prevalence for years 2005-2011 of children aged 6 years. ASD: autism spectrum disorder.

Figure 2. Choropleth of confirmed EBLL-10 of children <72 months for years 1999-2005. EBLL-10: elevated blood lead level ≥ 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dL}$.

Figure 3. Choropleth of weighted average of ZIP code-level population density derived from census year 2010 (persons per square mile).

EBLL-5D 1999

EBLL-5D 2000

EBLL-5D 2001

EBLL-5D 2002

EBLL-5D 2003

EBLL-5D 2004

EBLL-5D 2005

Figure 4. Choropleth of mean EBLL-5D transformed from EBLL-10 for years 1999-2005 based on mean ratio of EBLL-10 to EBLL-5 (5:10 ratio) for years 2010-2015. EBLL-5 acted as proxy indicator of maternal blood lead level from a period 6 years prior to ASD prevalence. EBLL-5D: derived prevalence of elevated blood lead level ≥ 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dL}$.

Figure 5. A) EBL-5D of children <72 months for years 1999-2005 vs. ASD prevalence (children aged 6 years) in 2005-2011 B) Population density (persons per square mile) vs. ASD prevalence in 2005-2011. EBL-5D: derived prevalence of elevated blood lead level $\geq 5 \mu\text{g/dL}$; ASD: autism spectrum disorder

A. EBLL-5D, 1999 (or first instance)

B. EBLL-5D, 2005

C. ASD, 2005 (or first instance)

D. ASD, 2011

Figure 6. Cluster maps indicate positive spatial autocorrelation (high-high, low-low regions) and negative spatial autocorrelation (high-low, and low-high regions) of ASD prevalence or EBLL-5D estimates. EBLL-5D: derived prevalence of elevated blood lead level ≥ 5 $\mu\text{g/dL}$